

BLOCK-COORDINATE DESCENT ALGORITHM FOR INTERVENTIONAL DATA IN DIRECTED GRAPHICAL MODELS

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Abstract

Computing maximum likelihood estimates in linear structural equation models is generally a difficult problem. The critical equations are usually non-linear and have numerous solutions, even for purely observational data. The block-coordinate descent (BCD) algorithm proposed by Drton et al. (2019)[1] is an efficient way to solve the optimization problem by decomposing it into a series of sub-problems with closed-form solutions, and which works with observational data. In this work, we describe the general problem of a BCD-type scheme for computing maximum likelihood estimates in linear structural equation models without hidden variables, integrating multiple observational and interventional environments. With interventional data, the degrees of both the original likelihood equations and the block-coordinate update equations could increase greatly. We study special setups in which the block optimization subproblems have a degree of at most 2 and provide closed-form solutions in these cases. Additionally, we discuss the potential applications of the model and algorithm to health and well-being data.

1 Introduction

Structural equation models (SEMs) encode the cause-effect relationships between random variables and error terms, and are widely used across various fields. Naturally, a structural equation model is associated with a directed (or mixed) graph, where the edges represent relations between variables. Research on structural equation models dates back to Wright's path diagrams (Wright, 1921, 1934), and Haavelmo's simultaneous equations (Haavelmo, 1943), with more recent integration into a general framework for causal modeling (Spirtes et al., 2000; Pearl, 2009).

In this work, we address the problem of computing maximum likelihood estimates (MLEs) in linear SEMs with Gaussian errors, using both observational and interventional data. For recursive SEMs with independent errors (represented by a directed

acyclic graph, DAG), the computation of MLEs with interventional data follows a similar approach as with observational data, involving regressing each node on its parental nodes using data from environments where the variable Y_i is not intervened (Hauser and Bühlmann, 2012; Hauser and Bühlmann, 2015). However, more general models may include bidirected edges and cycles, corresponding to hidden variables and self-regulatory feedback loops, respectively. For these models, quasi-Newton optimization and block-wise partial optimization methods have been proposed for purely observational scenarios. The R packages “sem” (Fox, 2006) and “lavaan” (Rosseel, 2012) use quasi-Newton methods. The residual iterative conditional fitting (RICF) algorithm gives a closed-form block update for acyclic directed mixed graph models (Drton et al., 2009). Recently, the block-coordinate descent (BCD) algorithm is proposed in Drton et al. (2019), extending the RICF algorithm to graphs with cycles.

Interventions across different environments induce variations in both the graph and equation structures, significantly increasing the complexity of the log-likelihood function and its optimization. Even in the purely observational case, the likelihood equations are typically high-degree algebraic functions of the data (Drton et al., 2019). The BCD algorithm attempts to perform low degree partial optimizations at each step for observational data. Extending the algorithm to accommodate both observational and interventional data is of great interest. However, for this extension, we focus on directed cyclic graphs without bidirected edges.

We consider linear SEMs associated with a directed graph and address the general question of BCD-type optimization. Several concrete examples of intervention targets, linear SEMs, and directed graphs are provided, along with the joint log-likelihood, critical point equations, and maximum likelihood degrees. For certain kinds of graphs and special intervention targets on arbitrary directed graphs, we show that the block update problem is a quadratic equation with degree 2. This indicates that the BCD-type method can still be applied to interventional data under certain conditions.

2 Linear structural equation models

2.1 Background

A structural equation model (SEM) is a equation system involving variables $Y_i : i \in V$ and stochastic errors $\{\epsilon_i : i \in V\}$, where V is the set of variables and $|V| = p$. It describes the quantitative mechanism by which a variable Y_i depends on other variables and their associated error. In this work, we adopt the notations introduced in Drton et al. (2019) and focus on linear SEMs with independent errors:

$$Y_i = \sum_{j \in V \setminus \{i\}} \beta_{ij} Y_j + \epsilon_i, \quad i \in V. \quad (1)$$

The coefficients can be summarized in an edge weight matrix $B = (\beta)_{ij}$ and we can express Y and ϵ in vector form

$$Y = BY + \epsilon, \quad \epsilon \sim N(0, \Omega),$$

where Ω is a (positive definite) diagonal matrix, and $\omega = \text{diag}(\Omega)$ denotes its diagonal part.

An SEM can be represented by a directed graph $G = (V, E)$, where the node set V corresponds to the random variables and the edge set E consists of ordered node pairs. A pair $(i, j) \in E$ defines a directed edge $i \rightarrow j \in G$, implying that Y_i has a causal effect on Y_j . In this context, we refer to i as a parent of j and j as a child of i : $i \in \text{pa}(j)$, $j \in \text{ch}(i)$. The weights of the parental edges of i are denoted by $B_{i, \text{pa}(i)}$. SEMs are not always recursive, meaning the associated graph may contain feedback loops. The strongly connected component (SCC) in a directed graph is a maximal subgraph in which there is a directed path between any pair of nodes. The strongly connected component that includes i in a directed graph G is denoted by $\mathcal{C}(i, G)$. When the graph is clear from context, we simply use $\mathcal{C}(i)$.

2.2 Interventional distributions

We are interested in data collected under different interventions. The type of interventions we consider are “hard” interventions that fix the values of the intervened variables in a randomized fashion so that they follow a controlled probability distribution (Pearl, 2009; Spirtes et al., 2000).

Throughout this paper, we use $I \subseteq V$ to denote the intervention target in one interventional environment, i.e., the set I indexes the intervened variables. Given an intervention target I , the manipulated graph G_I is obtained by removing all edges pointing to nodes in I from G , representing the structure of the SEM after the intervention. The collection $\mathcal{I} \subset 2^V$ denotes the family of intervention targets I_k ’s across all environments for which data is available. To distinguish from the entry indices in data matrices, we use (k) -superscripts to specify quantities from different interventional environments: $Y^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n^{(k)}}$ is the data matrix for intervention target I_k , where each column is one sample and $n^{(k)}$ is the sample size; the parameters $(\Omega^{(k)}, B^{(k)})$ differs because of interventions.

Example 1. *In Figure 1, the linear SEM in the observational environment is*

$$\begin{cases} Y_1 &= \epsilon_1, \\ Y_2 &= \beta_{21}Y_1 + \beta_{24}Y_4 + \epsilon_2, \\ Y_3 &= \beta_{32}Y_2 + \epsilon_3, \\ Y_4 &= \beta_{41}Y_1 + \beta_{43}Y_3 + \epsilon_4, \end{cases}, \quad (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_3, \epsilon_4)^T \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \text{diag}(\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4)).$$

With intervention target $I = \{2\}$, the manipulated linear SEM becomes

$$\begin{cases} Y_1 &= \epsilon_1, \\ Y_2 &= \epsilon'_2, \\ Y_3 &= \beta_{32}Y_2 + \epsilon_3, \\ Y_4 &= \beta_{41}Y_1 + \beta_{43}Y_3 + \epsilon_4, \end{cases}, \quad (\epsilon_1, \epsilon'_2, \epsilon_3, \epsilon_4)^T \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \text{diag}(\omega_1, \omega'_2, \omega_3, \omega_4)).$$

Figure 1: Original graph, and manipulated graph with intervention target $I = \{2\}$.

2.3 Likelihood inference

The log-likelihood of a single interventional dataset k is a function of $(\Omega^{(k)}, B^{(k)})$:

$$\ell_{G,Y}(\Omega^{(k)}, B^{(k)}) = -\log \det(\Omega^{(k)}) - \log \det(I - B^{(k)})^2 - \text{tr} \left\{ (I - B^{(k)})^T (\Omega^{(k)})^{-1} (I - B^{(k)}) S^{(k)} \right\},$$

where $S^{(k)} = Y^{(k)}(Y^{(k)})^T/n^{(k)}$ is the sample covariance matrix of the k 'th environment. And the total log-likelihood is

$$\ell_{G,Y^{(1)},\dots,Y^{(K)}}(\Omega, B) = \sum_k^K n^{(k)} \cdot \ell_{G,Y^{(k)}}(\Omega^{(k)}, B^{(k)}). \quad (2)$$

To find the critical point(s), we take derivatives to derive the likelihood equations, as demonstrated in Proposition 1 of Drton et al. (2019). Typically, the likelihood equations are of high degree. In example 1, the equations for $\mathcal{I} = \{\emptyset\}$ has degree 6 and the equations for $\mathcal{I} = \{\emptyset, \{2\}\}$ has degree 9.¹ Following the procedures outlined in Drton and Richardson (2004); Drton et al. (2019), we apply the block-coordinate descent method to break the original problem into partial subproblems of lower degrees.

3 Block-coordinate descent

3.1 Block update problem

For each node i , the total log-likelihood (2) can be written as a function of $(\omega_{ii}, B_{i,\text{pa}(i)})$

$$\begin{aligned} \ell_{G,Y^1,\dots,Y^K}(\omega_{ii}, B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}) = \sum_{k:i \notin I_k} \left(-n^{(k)} \log \omega_{ii}^{(k)} - \frac{1}{\omega_{ii}^{(k)}} \|Y_i^{(k)} - B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^{(k)}\|^2 \right. \\ \left. + n^{(k)} \log[(c_{i,0}^{(k)} + B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} c_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^{(k)})^2] \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

This expression follows the likelihood formula in Drton et al. (2019) and is based on the result that $\det(I - B^{(k)}) = c_{i,0}^{(k)} + B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} c_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^{(k)}$.²

¹See the accompanying Mathematica script.

²See Lemma 2 in Drton et al. (2019).

If $Y_i^{(k)} - B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^{(k)} \neq 0$ for each k such that $i \notin I_k$, then

$$(\omega_{ii}^{(k)})^* = \frac{1}{\sum_{k:i \notin I_k} n^{(k)}} \sum_{k:i \notin I_k} n^{(k)} \|Y_i^{(k)} - B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^{(k)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^{(k)}\|^2$$

maximizes the total log-likelihood with respect to $\omega_{ii}^{(k)}$. This leads to the following profile log-likelihood function for the parameter vector $B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}$:

$$\ell(B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}) = - \sum_{k:i \notin I_k} n^{(k)} \log \frac{\sum_{k:i \notin I_k} \|Y_i^{(k)} - B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^{(k)}\|^2}{(c_{i,0}^{(k)} + B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} c_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^{(k)})^2}. \quad (4)$$

3.2 Degree 2 update, condition and formula

In general, the block update problem is challenging to solve. Unless the graph structure is restricted, a closed-form update is only achievable under specific conditions on the interventions. For node i , such a closed-form update is possible if the following sufficient condition is met:

$$\exists G' \subseteq G, \text{ s.t. } \forall I \in \mathcal{I} \text{ and } i \notin I, \mathcal{C}(i, G_{\bar{I}}) = G' \text{ or } V[\mathcal{C}(i, G_{\bar{I}})] = \{i\}, \quad (5)$$

where the operator $V[\cdot]$ returns the set of the nodes in a (sub)graph. In other words, the condition requires that there could be at most 2 different structures of the strongly connected component containing i , and one of which is the singleton set $\{i\}$. For directed graphs where each strongly connected component contains **at most one cycle** (meaning any two cycles in the graph are disjoint), condition (5) is automatically satisfied for all nodes and any intervention family \mathcal{I} .

All the valid samples ($i \notin I_k$) are divided into these two groups, with total sample sizes n_1 and n_2 . To estimate $(\omega_{ii}, B_{i,\text{pa}(i)})$, we stack these data matrices $Y^{(k)}$ column-wise into a single matrix Y . If the $\mathcal{C}(i, G_{\bar{I}})$'s take values in $\{i\}$ and some G' across all I 's, the profile log-likelihood function after optimizing over ω_{ii} , is given by

$$g_i(B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}) = -n_1 \log \left(\frac{\|Y_i - B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}\|^2}{(c_{i,0} + B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} c_{i,\text{pa}(i)})^2} \right) - n_2 \log (\|Y_i - B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}\|^2) + C.$$

Maximizing the profile log-likelihood function is equivalent to this minimization problem

$$\min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{|\text{pa}(i)|}} n_1 \log \frac{\|Y_i^T - Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T \alpha\|^2}{(c_{i,0} + c_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^T \alpha)^2} + n_2 \log (\|Y_i^T - Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T \alpha\|^2). \quad (6)$$

Next, we demonstrate that by applying the reparameterization techniques outlined in Drton et al. (2019), the minimization problem in (6) admits closed-form solutions with algebraic degree 2.

Theorem 1. *Given a node i , let $n_1, n_2 > 0$ be the total numbers of data corresponding to strongly connected components G' and $\{i\}$, respectively, and let $r = n_1/n_2$. Suppose*

that the stacked partial data matrix $Y_{\text{pa}(i) \cup \{i\}}$ has full rank $|\text{pa}(i)| + 1 \leq n_1 + n_2$. Let $\hat{\alpha} = (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_i^T$ be the minimizer of $\|Y_i^T - Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T \alpha\|^2$. We define $n := n_1 + n_2$, $m := |\text{pa}(i)|$, $c_0 := c_{i,0}$ and $c_1 := c_{i,\text{pa}(i)} \neq 0$, $y_0^2 := \|Y_i^T - Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T \hat{\alpha}\|^2$ and $l^2 := c_1^T (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1$. Then the solution of the optimization problem in (6) satisfies

$$\alpha^* = \hat{\alpha} + \delta \cdot (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1, \quad (7)$$

where δ is a solution to the quadratic equation

$$l^2 \delta^2 + (c_1^T \hat{\alpha} + c_0)(r + 1)\delta - r y_0^2 = 0. \quad (8)$$

Proof. By adopting the orthogonal transformation method in Drton et al. (2019), we further derive auxiliary properties relevant to our problem.

First, we find an orthogonal $m \times m$ matrix Q_1 such that $Q_1 c_1 = (0, \dots, 0, \|c_1\|)^T$. Then, we compute a QR decomposition $Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T Q_1^T = Q_2^T R$, with $Q_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times m}$ orthogonal and $R \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times m}$ upper triangular. Since $Y_{\text{pa}(i)}$ and $Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T Q_1^T$ have full ranks, we can assume that all diagonal entries of R are positive, making the matrix R unique for any given Q_1 . After reparameterizing $\alpha' = Q_1 \alpha$, the common L_2 -norm term is transformed to

$$\begin{aligned} y_0^2 &= \|Y_i^T - Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T \alpha\|^2 = \|Q_2 Y_i^T - R \alpha'\|^2 \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^m [(Q_2 Y_i^T)_j - (R \alpha')_j]^2 + \sum_{j=m+1}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2, \end{aligned}$$

and the denominator is transformed to $(c_0 + \|c_1\| \alpha'_m)^2$.

Since $R = \begin{pmatrix} R_1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$ with $R_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, we reparameterize again with $\alpha'' = R_1 \alpha'$ and the original minimization problem becomes

$$\min_{\alpha'' \in \mathbb{R}^m} n_1 \log \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m [(Q_2 Y_i^T)_j - \alpha''_j]^2 + \sum_{j=m+1}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2}{(c_0 + \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} \alpha''_m)^2} + n_2 \log \left(\sum_{j=1}^m [(Q_2 Y_i^T)_j - \alpha''_j]^2 + \sum_{j=m+1}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2 \right). \quad (9)$$

Any solution must satisfy that $\alpha''_j = (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j$ for $j \in [m-1]$. The optimal value of α''_m is given by

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{\alpha''_m \in \mathbb{R}} \left\{ n_1 \log \frac{[(Q_2 Y_i^T)_m - \alpha''_m]^2 + \sum_{j=m+1}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2}{(c_0 + \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} \alpha''_m)^2} + n_2 \log \left([(Q_2 Y_i^T)_m - \alpha''_m]^2 + \sum_{j=m+1}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2 \right) \right\}, \quad (10)$$

i.e., maximizing

$$g_i(x) := n_1 \log \left(x + \frac{c_0 R_{mm}}{\|c_1\|} \right)^2 - (n_1 + n_2) \log \left(x^2 - 2(Q_2 Y_i^T)_m x + \sum_{j=m}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2 \right) + C.$$

The univariate function g_i has derivative

$$g'_i(x) = \frac{2n_1}{x + c_0 R_{mm} / \|c_1\|} - 2(n_1 + n_2) \frac{x - (Q_2 Y_i^T)_m}{x^2 - 2(Q_2 Y_i^T)_m x + \sum_{j=m}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2}.$$

Let $a = 1$, $b = -(Q_2 Y_i^T)_m$, $c = \sum_{j=m}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2$ and $\lambda = \|c_1\| / R_{mm} \neq 0$. The equation $g'_i(x) = 0$ has the form $ax^2 + 2bx + c = 0$. Using $r = n_1/n_2$, the two solutions are

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha''_m &= \frac{b\lambda(r-1) - ac_0(r+1) \pm \sqrt{(b\lambda(r-1) - ac_0(r+1))^2 + 4a\lambda(c\lambda r - bc_0(r+1))}}{2a\lambda} \\ &= -\frac{b}{a} + \frac{(b\lambda - ac_0)(r+1) \pm \sqrt{(b\lambda - ac_0)^2(r+1)^2 + 4(ac - b^2)\lambda^2 r}}{2a\lambda}. \end{aligned}$$

The optimal solution in original coordinates is $\alpha = Q_1^T R_1^{-1} \alpha''$. Since $R_1^{-1}(Q_2 Y_i^T)$ is the linear regression coefficient vector of $Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T Q_1^T$ on Y_i^T , we have

$$Q_1^T R_1^{-1} (Q_2 Y_i^T)_{[m]} = (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_i^T := \hat{\alpha}.$$

Let $e_{m,m} = (0, \dots, 0, 1)$ be the m -th canonical basis vector of \mathbb{R}^m and let $e_{m,N}$ be the m -th canonical basis vector of \mathbb{R}^N (i.e., the vector with a 1 in the m -th position and zeros elsewhere). Noticing that $R_{mm}^{-1}(Q_2 Y_i^T)_m$ is the m -th entry of $R_1^{-1}(Q_2 Y_i^T)_{[m]}$, and the last column of R_1^{-T} is $R_{mm}^{-1} e_{m,m}$, we can derive that

$$\lambda \cdot b = -\|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} (Q_2 Y_i^T)_m = -\langle Q_1 c_1, R_1^{-1} (Q_2 Y_i^T)_{[m]} \rangle = -\langle c_1, Q_1^T R_1^{-1} (Q_2 Y_i^T)_{[m]} \rangle = -c_1^T \hat{\alpha},$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} Q_1^T R_1^{-1} \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} e_{m,m} &= Q_1^T R_1^{-1} R_1^{-T} Q_1 c_1 = (Q_1^T R^T R Q_1)^{-1} c_1 \\ &= (Q_1^T R^T Q_2 Q_2^T R Q_1)^{-1} c_1 = (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1. \end{aligned}$$

The matrices Q_1 , Q_2 , and R may vary, but the value of R_{mm} (or equivalently, λ) is uniquely determined by $Y_{\text{pa}(i)}$ and c_1 . To see this, note that

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1 &= Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T Q_1^T R_1^{-1} \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} e_{m,m} = Q_2^T \begin{pmatrix} R_1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} R_1^{-1} \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} e_{m,m} \\ &= Q_2^T \begin{pmatrix} I_m \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} e_{m,m} = Q_2^T \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} e_{m,N}. \end{aligned}$$

Since Q_2 is orthogonal, the Euclidean norms of both sides must be equal. That is,

$$l = \sqrt{c_1^T (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1} = \|Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1\| = \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} = \lambda.$$

Then we can compute

$$c = b^2 + \sum_{j=m+1}^N (Q_2 Y_i^T)_j^2 = b^2 + \|Y_i^T - Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T \hat{\alpha}\|^2 = b^2 + y_0^2,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha''_m &= -b + \frac{(-c_1^T \hat{\alpha} - c_0)(r+1) \pm \sqrt{(c_1^T \hat{\alpha} + c_0)^2 (r+1)^2 + 4rl^2 y_0^2}}{2l} \\ &:= (Q_2 Y_i^T)_{[m]} + \frac{(-c_1^T \hat{\alpha} - c_0)(r+1) \pm \sqrt{\Delta_{r,\hat{\alpha}}(l)}}{2l}\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the two possible optimal vectors are

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha &= Q_1^T R_1^{-1} (Q_2 Y_i^T)_{[m]} + \frac{-(c_1^T \hat{\alpha} + c_0)(r+1) \pm \sqrt{\Delta_{r,\hat{\alpha}}(l)}}{2l^2} \|c_1\| R_{mm}^{-1} \cdot Q_1^T R_1^{-1} e_{m,m} \\ &= \hat{\alpha} + \frac{-(c_1^T \hat{\alpha} + c_0)(r+1) \pm \sqrt{\Delta_{r,\hat{\alpha}}(l)}}{2l^2} (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1.\end{aligned}$$

Each possible solution is the simple linear regression coefficient vector $\hat{\alpha}$ adding a multiple of $(Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1$. The coefficient of the second term is a solution to the quadratic equation

$$l^2 t^2 + (c_1^T \hat{\alpha} + c_0)(r+1)t - r y_0^2 = 0,$$

where $\hat{\alpha} = Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} Y_i^T$, $y_0^2 = \|Y_i^T - Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T \hat{\alpha}\|^2$ and $l^2 = \|Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T (Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1\|^2$. \square

The update of ω_{ii} is given by

$$\omega_{ii}^* = \frac{1}{n_1 + n_2} \|Y_i - B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^* Y_{\text{pa}(i)}\|^2 \quad (11)$$

for the two possible $B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^*$'s. Then the profile log-likelihood has value

$$n_1 \log((c_{i,0} + B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^* c_{i,\text{pa}(i)})^2) - (n_1 + n_2) \log(\omega_{ii}^*) + C. \quad (12)$$

The choice of $B_{i,\text{pa}(i)}^*$ corresponds to the larger log-likelihood value of the two candidates.

Remark 1.1. *The ratio $r = n_1/n_2$ influences the possible weights in the direction of $(Y_{\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T)^{-1} c_1$. When $n_2 = 0$, or equivalently $r = \infty$, the problem reduces to the purely observational case. In this scenario, equation (8) simplifies to a linear form: $(c_1^T \hat{\alpha} + c_0)t - y_0^2 = 0$, which coincides with the result established in Drton et al. (2019).*

At each update, the block-coordinate descent algorithm finds a local maximum of log-likelihood function with respect to a subset of all variables. Overall, the value of the log-likelihood function is non-decreasing throughout the iterations. To ensure that the algorithm is well-defined, each block update must have an optimal solution in which every ω_{ii} positive. This condition is equivalent to requiring $\|Y_i - B_{i,\text{pa}(i)} Y_{\text{pa}(i)}\| > 0$ during the update for every i , which in turn implies that Y_i is not in the row span $Y_{\text{pa}(i)}$, i.e., the matrix $Y_{\text{pa}(i) \cup \{i\}}$ has linearly independent rows. This requirement is consistent with condition (A1) _{i} in Drton et al. (2019) for directed graphs. Using similar arguments, we can conclude that for generic triples $(Y, \omega_0, B_0) \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times N} \times \omega(V) \times \mathbf{B}(G)$, any finite number of iterations of Algorithm 1 have unique and feasible block updates when (ω_0, B_0) is used as the starting value.

Input: $\omega^0, B^0; Y^{(1)}, \dots, Y^{(K)}; I_1, \dots, I_K$ and n_1, \dots, n_K

```

repeat
    foreach  $i \in V$  do
        if the condition (5) does not hold then
            | stop: The block update cannot be solved in closed-form;
        end
        Find  $S_2 = \{k : I_k \in \mathcal{I}_{-i}, \mathcal{C}(i, G_{\overline{k}}) = \{i\}\}$ ;
        Find  $S_1 = \{k : I_k \in \mathcal{I}_{-i}\} \setminus S_2$ ;
        Set  $Y = [Y^{(k_1)}, \dots, Y^{(k_l)}]$  with  $k_1, \dots, k_l \in S_1 \cup S_2$ ;
        Compute  $n_1 = \sum_{k \in S_1} n_k$  and  $n_2 = \sum_{k \in S_2} n_k$ ;
        if  $n_1 = 0$  then
            | Compute  $\hat{B}_{i, \text{pa}(i)}$  by solving least squares:  $\arg \min_{\beta} \|Y_i^T - Y_{\text{pa}(i)}^T \beta\|^2$ ;
        else
            if  $n_2 = 0$  then
                | Compute  $\hat{B}_{i, \text{pa}(i)}$  as the block-coordinate update for observational
                | data;
            else
                | Compute the two possible  $\hat{B}_{i, \text{pa}(i)}$  using (7) and (8);
                | Compute corresponding  $\hat{\omega}_{ii}$  and log-likelihood values using (11)
                | and (12);
                | Choose the larger log-likelihood value and the corresponding
                |  $(\hat{\omega}_{ii}, \hat{B}_{i, \text{pa}(i)})$ ;
            end
        end
        end
        Update  $\omega$  and  $B_i$  using  $\hat{\omega}_{ii}$  and  $\hat{B}_{i, \text{pa}(i)}$ ;
    end
until convergence criterion is met;
    
```

Algorithm 1: Block-coordinate descent, for directed graph and special intervention targets

4 Numerical experiments

Suppose there are K dataset with different interventions $\mathcal{I} = \{I_1, \dots, I_K\}$, the simple aggregation method involves performing original BCD algorithm on each dataset, aggregating the K MLEs and compute the weighted average as the final estimates. A natural choice of weighting scheme is to use weights proportional to the sample sizes. We compare the performance of the simple aggregation method and our BCD-type algorithms on synthetic data.

In the simulations, we consider the special directed graphs that contain one unique cycle. First, we add the l -cycle $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow l \rightarrow 1$ to the empty graph. Due to the component constraint, there remain $p(p-1)/2 - l(l-1)/2$ ordered pairs (i, j) with $i < j$ that can be assigned with nonzero edge weights. We simulate independent

uniform random variables $U_{ij} \sim U(0, 1)$. If $U_{ij} < d$, the edge $i \rightarrow j$ is introduced. The sparsity parameter $d \in (0, 1)$ controls the average number of edges in the graph. The edge generation is performed under a fixed topological ordering of the nodes. After adding the edges, we randomly permute the node labels. This construction ensures that the graph has a unique cycle of length l .

p	m	k	d	RMSE		diff-llh		Running time	
				Agg	MLE	Agg	MLE	Agg	MLE
5	25	0	0.2	0.0277	0.0267	0.2426	0.2274	1.04	0.63
5	25	0	0.3	0.0280	0.0266	0.2861	0.2629	1.07	0.86
5	25	3	0.2	0.2281	0.1732	0.3731	0.3020	10.71	3.92
5	25	3	0.3	0.2141	0.1498	0.4104	0.3282	11.16	4.00
5	25	4	0.2	0.0319	0.0901	0.3673	0.3170	9.08	4.19
5	25	4	0.3	0.0323	0.0989	0.3913	0.3367	9.02	4.45
5	50	0	0.2	0.0134	0.0130	0.1046	0.1010	0.97	0.63
5	50	0	0.3	0.0135	0.0130	0.1204	0.1144	1.08	0.70
5	50	3	0.2	0.0353	1.1436*	0.1686	0.1350	11.89	4.04
5	50	3	0.3	0.0339	1.0413*	0.1810	0.1440	11.93	4.21
5	50	4	0.2	0.0154	0.0124	0.1600	0.1417	8.70	4.09
5	50	4	0.3	0.0156	0.0125	0.1676	0.1477	8.86	4.06
10	50	0	0.2	0.0106	0.0100	0.2358	0.2147	2.24	1.48
10	50	0	0.3	0.0113	0.0104	0.3093	0.2714	2.60	1.72
10	50	3	0.2	0.0330	0.0112	0.2894	0.2401	16.99	5.84
10	50	3	0.3	0.0300	0.0113	0.3745	0.2932	18.72	6.20
10	50	4	0.2	0.0109	0.0098	0.2952	0.2533	13.23	5.35
10	50	4	0.3	0.0116	0.0101	0.3699	0.3045	14.03	5.72
10	100	0	0.2	0.0053	0.0051	0.1098	0.1053	2.21	1.58
10	100	0	0.3	0.0054	0.0051	0.1400	0.1314	2.70	2.02
10	100	3	0.2	0.0074	0.0057	0.1296	0.1126	18.24	6.20
10	100	3	0.3	0.0072	0.0057	0.1599	0.1356	19.76	6.64
10	100	4	0.2	0.0053	0.0048	0.1293	0.1169	13.44	5.51
10	100	4	0.3	0.0055	0.0049	0.1564	0.1380	14.49	5.97

Table 1: Statistics for randomly generated directed graphs with at most one unique cycle. Each row summarizes 1000 simulations. The columns "Agg" and "MLE" correspond to the aggregation method and Algorithm 1. "RMSE" represents the average root mean square error of the estimate for a single parameter among the total 1000 simulations. "diff-llh" is the average difference between the log-likelihood of the true parameters and that of the estimated parameters (the smaller the better). Running time is the average CPU time (in milliseconds). For the aggregation method, the reported running time includes both the BCD algorithm applied to each observational or interventional dataset and the subsequent aggregation steps.

We use 24 different configurations of (p, m, l, d) , where m is the sample size of observational data. For each graph, we randomly select the number of interventional environments, ensuring that $|\mathcal{I}| \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Each random intervention target is of size 2 or 3. We then compute the intervened model and simulate data of sample size $\max(m_k, p+1)$, $n_k \sim U[\lfloor (m+1)/2 \rfloor, m]$, for each intervention target. Consequently, the data for one graph is from both observation and interventions, with the total size ranging between $3m/2$ and $4m$. We consider $p \in \{5, 10\}$, $m \in \{5p, 10p\}$, and $l \in \{0, 3, 4\}$, with $d \in \{0.2, 0.3\}$.

We avoid using 2-cycles because they are not identifiable from observational data (Drton et al., 2019), and estimation results with interventional data are also unstable.

For each of the configurations (p, m, l, d) , we simulate 1000 graphs using the procedure described above. In each simulation, all free entries of B are drawn independently from a uniform distribution on $[-2, -0.5] \cup [0.5, 2]$. The diagonal entries of Ω are randomly drawn from a uniform distribution on $[0.3, 1]$. For an intervention target set I , the corresponding columns in B are masked by zero: $B_{I,\cdot} = 0$. The interventional errors ϵ_I are sampled from $|I|$ independent standard normal distributions.

Simulations were performed on a desktop equipped with an AMD Ryzen 9 7950X3D processor (4.2 GHz), using R 4.4.2 on Windows 11. For each run, the maximum number of iterations was set to 5000. In all simulations, our algorithm converged, and the BCD algorithm also converged across all environments. Table 1 summarizes the simulation results.

Our MLE algorithm consistently achieves higher log-likelihood values and outperforms the aggregation method in terms of RMSE across most of the configurations. There are 2 exceptions where our method does not achieve lower RMSE. The RMSE may be influenced by extreme values in cycle parameter estimation, whereas the likelihood-based metric tends to be more stable. This behavior reflects the nature of cyclic models, where better likelihood does not necessarily imply a smaller RMSE due to the additional likelihood contribution from the cycle structure. In addition to achieving higher accuracy, our MLE algorithm is also faster than the aggregation method, as expected.

For real data example, one potential application is to model the relations between daily sleeping time, activity time and mental health measurements using data collected in the Healthy Aging in Industrial Environment study - Program 4 (4HAIE) (Elavsky et al., 2021). Beginning in 2019, this study intensively monitored air pollution and behavioral parameters. The timing of the study coincided with the COVID-19 and the pandemic restrictive measures implemented since March 2020 can be regarded as interventions affecting activity patterns (e.g., steps per day). After transforming the data to standard normal scale, variables corresponding to average sleeping time, average daily steps, and psychological scores fit naturally within a linear SEM framework that includes a feedback loop. Data collected before and after the implementation of the restrictive measures serve as observational and interventional data, respectively.

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